

FRACTURE BEHAVIOR OF EPOXY/CLAY AND EPOXY/SILICA NANOCOMPOSITES

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SUMMARY: The change of the fracture toughness and its dependence on the nanoparticles content and adhesion at the interface of epoxy matrix and nanoparticles are discussed. Several clay and silica particles, whose surface treatments were different, were used in this investigation. To fabricate the nanocomposites, the nanoparticles were sonicated in acetone for 1-2 hours using a solution technique. The bright field TEM micrographs showed excellent dispersion of nanoparticles in epoxy matrix. Both intercalation and exfoliation of clay platelets were observed dependent on clay modifications. The compact tension specimens were used for fracture testing. Fracture toughness increased with increasing clay content. The values of fracture toughness and critical energy release rate varied due to different clay morphology in epoxy matrix.

KEY WORDS: Confocal Laser Scanning Microscopy, Electron Microscopy, Epoxy Nanocomposites, Fracture, Organomontmorillonite

INTRODUCTION

The utility of using exfoliated smectite clay platelets as reinforcements in organic polymers has been reported over the past decade. Studies have documented the processing, mechanical, and thermal characteristics of epoxy/clay nanocomposites [1-7], and it has especially been clarified that epoxy/clay nanocomposites have an excellent improvement of elastic modulus. The clay particles were chemically modified to disperse with intercalation and exfoliation. However, the fracture behavior of nanocomposites has little been observed. The interface region increases after more clay particles were added into epoxy system. Therefore the bonding condition at the interface of nano-scale fillers and epoxy matrix is absolutely crucial to improve fracture toughness with increasing amount of nano-scale particles.

In this paper, epoxy/clay and epoxy/silica nanocomposites were prepared with different surface treatments and modifications. The fracture behavior of these anhydride-cured epoxy based nanocomposites is investigated. The morphology of nano particles in epoxy matrix is observed by transmission electron microscopy, and the fracture toughness and the critical energy release rates of anhydride-cured epoxy based nanocomposites are measured with compact tension (CT) specimens. Critical energy release rate is correlated with fracture surface roughness for epoxy/clay nanocomposites.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials a) Clay Nanocomposites Diglycidyl ether of bisphenol A (DGEBA, Epon 828, Shell Chemicals Inc., epoxide equivalent weight=189), epoxidized polyol (DER 736, The Dow Chemical Company, epoxide equivalent weight=190), methyltetrahydrophthalicanhydride (MTHPA, Aradur™ HY 917 Vantico Inc., equivalent weight=159) and imidazole (DY 070, Vantico Inc.) were used for main component, reactive diluent, anhydride curing agent, and accelerator. The mixing ratio by weight was Epon 828: DER 736: HY 917: DY 070=100:100:168:2.00. To understand the effect of surface treatment of clay particles, organomontmorillonite clay modified with methyl, tallow, bis(2-hydroxyethyl) quaternary ammonium (MT2EtOH) ion (Cloisite 30B, Southern Clay Products Inc., denoted as Sample A), modified with octadecyl trimethyl ammonium (ODTMA) ion (Nanomar I.28E, Nanocor Inc., denoted as Sample B), and smectite clay without any modification (Lucentite SWN, Co-op Chemical Co. Ltd., denoted as Sample C) were used as clay reinforcements. Since it has been previously confirmed by dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA) that stoichiometry was maintained without adjusting

the quantity of curing agent, the clay particles were simply added to process 2.5-15.0 wt. % nanocomposites. To fabricate the nanocomposites, the clay was sonicated in acetone for two hours using a solution concentration of more than 30 liters of acetone to 1 kilogram of clay. The epoxy resin and the reactive diluent were then added and mixed with a magnetic stirrer for an additional hour. The acetone was removed by vacuum extraction at 100 °C for 24 hours, after which time the anhydride curing agent was blended into the solution with a magnetic stirrer. The specimens were cured at 80 °C for 4 hours, and then postcured at 160 °C for 2 hours.

b) Silica Nanocomposites Diglycidyl ether of bisphenol F (DGEBF, Epon 862, Shell Chemicals Inc., epoxide equivalent weight=172) was used for main component. The mixing ratio by weight was Epon 862:HY 917:DY 070=100:92.7:1.00. To understand the effect of surface treatment of clay particles, 3 different nano-silica particles, which are non-treated (M-5,

Cabot Corporation, denoted as Sample D), treated with hexamethyldisilazane (TS-530, Cabot Corporation, denoted as Sample E), and treated with polydimethylsiloxane (TS-720, Cabot Corporation, denoted as Sample F), were used as silica reinforcements. The nano-silica particles were simply added to process 2.5-5.0 wt. % nanocomposites. To fabricate the nanocomposites, the silica was sonicated in acetone for an hour using a solution concentration of more than 30 liters of acetone to 1 kilogram of silica. Other processing procedures were the same as that for clay nanocomposites mentioned above.

Transmission electron microscope The exfoliated/intercalated clay layers and silica particles in the anhydride-cured epoxy matrix were observed with transmission electron microscopy (TEM). Thin sections of at least 70 nm were obtained at room temperature by ultramicrotomy with a diamond knife having an included angle of 4°. A JEOL 100CX TEM with LaB₆ filament in 120 kV or a JEOL 2010 TEM with field emission filament in 200 kV was used to collect images of the epoxy based nanocomposites.

Dynamic mechanical analysis Dynamic mechanical properties were collected with a TA Instruments DMA 2980 operating in the three-point bending mode at an oscillation frequency of 1.0 Hz. Data were collected from ambient to 170 °C at a scanning rate of 2 °C/min. A minimum of 3 specimens of each composition were tested.

Fracture testing The CT specimens were prepared for fracture testing. The configurations of the CT specimens are shown in Fig. 1. The crack length a , the width W , and the thickness B of specimens were determined as 10 mm, 20 mm, and 5 mm, respectively, based on ASTM D 5045 standard. The crack was firstly made by a band saw, and then the sharp initial crack tip was produced by a guillotine crack initiator and a razor blade. The crack length was measured by optical microscopy after completing the fracture testing. The applied load was measured by a load cell whose maximum capacity is 4.44 kN (1.00 klbf). The experiments were performed with a crosshead velocity of 15 mm/min to load the CT specimens. Displacement at the loading point was calculated from the crosshead travel. The fracture toughness was measured with at least 3 specimens for each different nanocomposite material at room temperature. The critical energy release rate was calculated from the fracture toughness in a plane-strain state.

Fractographic observations Fracture surfaces of CT specimens were observed by Philips ElectroScan 2020 Environmental Scanning Electron Microscope (ESEM) at 20 kV, after the fracture surfaces were coated with Au thin films. Zeiss LSM 210 Confocal laser scanning microscope (CLSM) was used to acquire 2-dimensional surface profiles and topography maps of fracture surfaces to evaluate fracture surface roughness. A 50X lens at a magnification of 50 was used to produce a field size of approximately 120 μm * 80 μm. At least 10 topography images were acquired for each different composition at a random location on the fracture surface near the initial

Fig. 1 Configuration of CT specimen.

Figure 2. TEM micrograph of anhydride-cured epoxy /MT2EtOH clay nanocomposites (Sample A).

Figure 3. TEM micrograph of anhydride-cured epoxy /ODTMA clay nanocomposites (Sample B).

Figure 4. TEM micrograph of anhydride-cured epoxy /non-treated clay nanocomposites (Sample C).

sonication, clay platelets were almost perfectly exfoliated and homogeneously dispersed. Only few platelets sometimes stack with one another, and it is extremely difficult to measure a d-spacing because of the good exfoliation and dispersion. On the other hand, the length of the clay platelets became much shorter than before due to the sonication process. In Fig. 2, the length of exfoliated clay platelets was measured in the range of 70-380 nm which was considerably shorter than the original length of 750nm to 1.2 microns.

Figure 3 shows a TEM micrograph of Sample B. Though the groups of clay platelets were homogeneously spread, a lot of clay platelets were only intercalated; each clay platelets were not homogeneously dispersed. The d-spacing and the length of the intercalated clay platelets was measured as 2.53-3.52 nm and 450 nm, respectively, in this TEM micrograph. In other regions, the longer clay platelets were also observed. In both Figs 2 and 3, debonding at the clay/epoxy interface was not observed by TEM. Therefore, the bonding condition at the epoxy/clay interface can be considered as perfect, thanks to the clay modification with both MT2EtOH and ODTMA.

Figure 4 shows a TEM micrograph of Sample C. No exfoliated clay platelets were observed in this sample because of a lack of clay modification. The d-spacing in this micrograph was measured as at least 2.09 nm. Since the original d-spacing of non-modified clay platelets was 1.17 nm, the clay platelets were intercalated and d-spacing was expanded despite the lack of clay modification. It was because acetone provided the possibility to penetrate DGEBA and reactive diluent into spaces between clay layers.

TEM observations of epoxy/silica nanocomposites Figures 5 and 6 show TEM micrographs of Samples D and F, respectively. Another TEM micrograph of sample E showed similar morphology as Sample F. The size

crack tip. All images were filtered to reduce noise, and then adjusted with tilt correction to evaluate arithmetic mean deviation R_a of fracture surface profile.

Izod pendulum impact resistance Izod impact strength was measured with 453 g (1.0 lb) pendulum for neat epoxy and epoxy/clay nanocomposites at room temperature. Izod impact specimens with the same dimension as indicated in ASTM D256 were used.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

TEM observations of epoxy/clay nanocomposites

Figure 2 shows a TEM micrograph of Sample A. Because of the suitable clay modification and ultra-

of individual silica nanoparticles were measured as at least 20 nm, and the size of silica aggregation was in a range of 40-450 nm in Figs. 5 and 6, though the size of silica particles before sonication was 200-300nm. Consequently, it was confirmed that sonication process for nanosilica particles in acetone provided excellent dispersion of silica nanoparticles in epoxy matrix.

Dynamic mechanical analysis

Figure 7 shows the relation between storage modulus of epoxy/clay nanocomposites measured by DMA at 30 °C and clay content for Samples A, B, and C. Since the d-spacing of Samples B and C is small in intercalation stage as discussed with TEM micrographs, it was measured by DMA that not the exfoliation but the intercalation of Sample B resulted in the lower storage modulus rather than Sample A.

Figure 8 shows the relation between storage modulus of epoxy/silica nanocomposites measured by DMA at 30 °C and volume percent of silica content for Samples D, E, and F. The storage modulus tended to linearly increase with increasing silica content. No difference was observed regarding different surface treatment for silica particles. The storage moduli in Figs. 7 and 8 were used as the elastic moduli to calculate the

Figure 5. TEM micrograph of anhydride-cured epoxy /non-treated silica nanocomposites (Sample D).

Figure 6. TEM micrograph of anhydride-cured epoxy /surface-treated silica nanocomposites (Sample F).

Figure 7. TEM micrograph of anhydride-cured epoxy /non-treated silica nanocomposites (Sample D).

Figure 8. TEM micrograph of anhydride-cured epoxy /surface treated silica nanocomposites (Sample F).

Figure 9. Change of fracture toughness with changing clay content.

Figure 10. Change of critical energy release rate with changing clay content.

critical energy release rate from the fracture toughness in a following section.

Fracture testing The non-linearity was seldom observed in load-displacement diagrams of neat epoxy and nanocomposites. Therefore, the maximum load was used to evaluate fracture toughness. Figure 9 shows the relation between the fracture toughness K_{IC} and clay content in vol.%. For Sample A, the fracture toughness was slightly increased after adding 2.5 wt.% clay platelets, compared with the value of neat epoxy. No difference was observed between 2.5 wt.% and 5.0 wt.% nanocomposites. Nanocomposites containing 7.5 wt.% exfoliated clay platelets showed a much lower fracture toughness rather than neat epoxy. For Sample B, the fracture toughness obviously increased with increasing the clay content up to 5.0 wt.%, and then the value reached a plateau. The testing of Specimen C showed no toughening effect with non-modified clay platelets.

The toughening effect can also be compared with the critical energy release rate as shown in Fig. 10. In this figure, it is obvious that the intercalated clay nanocomposites (Sample B) needed more energy for crack propagation than the exfoliated clay nanocomposites, comparing Samples A and B, since the fracture toughness of Sample B in Fig. 9 increased and the storage modulus of Sample B in Fig. 7 was not increased. On the other

Figure 11. Change of fracture toughness with changing silica content.

Figure 12. Change of critical energy release rate with changing silica content.

hand, Sample A showed less improvement in fracture toughness in Fig. 9 though the elastic modulus improved in Fig. 7. The size of intercalated clay platelets is larger than the size of plastic zone at the vicinity of the crack tip, and consequently the crack opening was prevented due to the bridging effect behind of the crack tip. On the other hand, this bridging effect cannot be expected because of much shorter length of perfectly exfoliated clay platelets, which is smaller than the size of plastic zone near the crack tip. It should also be noted that the critical energy release rate decreased after adding a certain amount of clay particles. However, the highest critical release rate of Samples A and B was obtained with different clay content. Therefore, the optimum amount of clay particles for the best toughening is dependent on the exfoliation and intercalation conditions of clay platelets. Comparing Specimens B and C, the important difference is the clay modification. Because of the lack of chemical treatment for clay, adequate bonding of the epoxy/clay interface should not be expected.

Figures 11 and 12 show the change of fracture toughness and critical energy release rate with changing silica content, respectively. Both fracture toughness and critical energy release rate were improved after adding

Figure 13. ESEM micrograph of fracture surface of anhydride-cured neat epoxy.

Figure 14. ESEM micrograph of fracture surface of anhydride-cured epoxy/MT2EtOH clay nano-composites (Sample A).

Figure 15. ESEM micrograph of fracture surface of anhydride-cured epoxy/ODTMA clay nanocomposites (Sample B).

Figure 16. ESEM micrograph of fracture surface of anhydride-cured epoxy/non-treated clay nano-composites (Sample C).

silica nanoparticles though the improvement rate was smaller than that of clay content. The smaller improvement rate is because of smaller aspect ratio (~1) of silica particles. The better toughening effect is obtained from inclusions having higher aspect ratio even if the inclusions of composites are randomly oriented in matrix. In Figs 11 and 12, no clear difference between Samples D, E, and F was observed regardless of different surface treatment of silica nanoparticles. One possible explanation was that hydroxyls on the non-treated silica nanoparticle surfaces can react with anhydride curing agent. This resulted in excellent adhesion at the interface between epoxy matrix and non-treated silica nanoparticles as well as surface-treated silica nanoparticles.

Fractographic observations Figures 13-16 show different morphology of fracture surface of neat epoxy and samples A, B, and C having 2.5 wt.% clay content. It was observed by ESEM that the fracture surface of neat epoxy in Fig. 13 was extremely flat, and that of Sample C showed a similar morphology in Fig. 16. The fracture surfaces of Samples A and B (Figs. 14 and 15, respectively) were much rougher than those of neat epoxy and Sample C, and this suggests the excellent bonding condition at the epoxy/clay interface thanks to the clay modification with MT2EtOH and ODTMA.

CLSM is a useful method to quantify surface roughness, which can be correlated with critical energy release rate. First, phi-z measurements of 2.5 wt.% exfoliated and intercalated nanocomposites (Samples A and B) were conducted. Figure 17 shows the 2-dimensional profiles of 2 different fracture surfaces. When the number of peaks of 2-D profile lines as shown in Fig.

(a) Anhydride-cured epoxy/MT2EtOH clay nanocomposites (Sample A).

(b) Anhydride-cured epoxy/ODTMA clay nanocomposites (Sample B).
Figure 17. Examples of 2-D profile of fracture surfaces.

(a) Epoxy/MT2EtOH clay nanocomposites (Sample A). (b) Epoxy /ODTMA clay nanocomposites (Sample B).
Figure 18. Examples of 3-D topography measurements of fracture surfaces.

17 was measured for modified intercalated and exfoliated clay nanocomposite samples, the average values of the number of peaks were 48 and 40 for exfoliated and intercalated nanocomposite samples, respectively. It can be thought the number of peaks for both samples were extremely close. Second, topography measurements of fracture surfaces of all samples were conducted to analyze arithmetic mean deviation of profile R_a and maximum height of profile R_{max} as shown in Fig. 18. Not only R_a but also R_{max} of Sample B were approximately 3 times larger than those of Sample A at any clay content. Because of these facts, the surface area of intercalated sample was obviously larger than that of exfoliated sample as well as the roughness value. Consequently, the critical energy release rate was correlated with R_a as shown in Fig. 19. Larger energy is necessary for crack propagation when the fracture surface area is larger. In another word, toughening effect was enormous when the clay particles were intercalated, as the fracture surface area became larger.

In conclusion, the model of crack propagation for both intercalated and exfoliated nanocomposites can be shown as Fig. 20 when the excellent adhesion was obtained at the interface of epoxy matrix and clay particles. For intercalated clay nanocomposites, the crack tends to avoid reaching the aggregations of intercalated clay particles, since the adhesion at the clay/epoxy interface was excellent and the strength of clay aggregation prevents crack from propagating. Therefore, the crack tends to curve at the micron level, and this results in the higher critical energy release rate with a rougher fracture surface. On the other hand for exfoliated clay nanocomposites, it is easy to break each individual clay platelet because of the small thickness of ~ 1 nm which is not strong enough to prevent the crack from propagating. The inclusions smaller than the size of plastic zone near the crack tip are not effective for prevention of the crack propagation. The fracture surface was still rough compared to that of neat epoxy, but obviously less rough rather than the intercalated nanocomposites. Consequently the fracture path tends to propagate straightforward through the exfoliated clay, and the good toughening effect cannot be expected. For non-modified intercalated

Figure 19. Relation between critical energy release rate and fracture surface roughness for anhydride-cured epoxy/clay nanocomposites.

(a) Intercalated clay nanocomposites.

(b) Exfoliated clay nanocomposites.

Figure 20. Models of crack propagation.

Figure 21 Change of Izod impact strength with regard to clay content.

clay nanocomposites, the excellent bonding of epoxy/clay interface could not be expected because of the lack of chemical treatment for clay. In fact, it was observed by ESEM that the fracture surface of neat epoxy was extremely flat, and that of non-modified intercalated clay nanocomposites showed a similar morphology as discussed with Fig. 16.

Izod impact strength Figure 21 shows the relation between Izod impact strength and clay content in the anhydride cured epoxy matrix. Regardless of clay morphology and clay modification, the impact strength decreased approximately 15 % when up to 5.0 wt.% clay was added, and then decreased to a constant value. Anhydride curing agent produces a rigid epoxy material, and this result shows that it is difficult to improve Izod impact strength for rigid epoxy material after adding clay particles.

CONCLUSIONS

The morphology of the exfoliated and intercalated clay layers was observed by TEM. The different reinforcing effect of exfoliated and intercalated clay platelets was measured by DMA. Clay modification with both MT2EtOH and ODTMA was effective to achieve excellent bonding at the epoxy/clay interface, and thus the fracture toughness was improved. The intercalated clay platelets provided a better toughening effect because of the larger ‘effective’ platelet size than the perfectly exfoliated clay platelets. Fracture toughness was also improved after adding silica nanoparticles whose aspect ratio is much smaller than that of clay platelets. No difference of fracture toughness was observed for silica nanocomposites regardless of surface treatment due to excellent adhesion between silica nanoparticles and anhydride cured epoxy matrix. Relation of critical energy release rate of clay nanocomposites and roughness of fracture surfaces was correlated using CLSM. Izod impact strength was reduced after adding clay particles regardless of clay modification and clay morphology in epoxy matrix.

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